

Hybrid Hydrogen Energy Storage System Living Lab

Alexandros Kafetzis ^{1,2,*}

¹ ARTEMIS Laboratory, Chemical Process and Energy Resources Institute, Centre for Research and Technology Hellas, 57001 Thessaloniki, Greece

² School of Mechanical Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, 54124 Thessaloniki, Greece

* Correspondence: akafetzi@certh.gr

Abstract

Hybrid hydrogen energy storage systems are increasingly considered for renewable integration in rural and weak-grid contexts, yet much of the literature remains simulation-based, site-specific, or insufficiently explicit about control and operational performance. This paper examines a hybrid hydro–PV–battery–hydrogen system operated at the Agkistron Living Lab in Northern Greece and assesses the role of layered storage in renewable surplus valorization and resilience-oriented operation. This study combines a system architecture description, a supervisory energy management strategy based on Hybrid Automata, and analysis of field data under both grid-connected and intentional off-grid conditions. The installation integrates hydropower, photovoltaics, battery storage, alkaline electrolysis, hydrogen storage, and PEMFCs. The results show that during on-grid operation, the EMS prioritizes battery charging and then hydrogen production, enabling high renewable utilization and low curtailment while preparing reserves for outages. During a 48 h intentional islanding event, the battery and hydrogen pathway operated sequentially, achieving an autonomy index of 82%, compared with 36% for the battery-only benchmark. Although the hydrogen pathway showed lower round-trip efficiency than battery-only storage, it substantially extended off-grid autonomy and continuity of supply. The findings support hybrid battery–hydrogen storage as a transferable operating concept for rural systems where renewable surplus and resilience requirements coexist.

Keywords: hybrid hydrogen energy storage; renewable energy; living lab; resilience; energy management

1. Introduction

The transition toward decarbonized energy systems requires substantial integration of renewable energy sources (RES) in remote and rural areas where grid expansion remains economically prohibitive and technically challenging [1]. While hydropower provides reliable baseload generation, small hydropower plants may still generate periods of renewable surplus that cannot be fully utilized locally or exported under favorable conditions, especially under limited interconnection capacity or weak tariff structures. Even reservoir-buffered small hydro facilities, although more flexible than purely run-of-river systems, remain exposed to grid export limits and mismatches between generation and local demand [2,3]. At the same time, battery energy storage systems (BESS) are widely used for short-duration balancing because of their high round-trip efficiency and fast response, but they may not be sufficient when the required storage duration extends beyond short-term flexibility and into multi-day backup or longer-duration energy shifting [4–6].

Received: 21 April 2026

Revised: 6 May 2026

Accepted: 11 May 2026

Published: 13 May 2026

Copyright: © 2026 by the authors. Licensee MDPI, Basel, Switzerland. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the [Creative Commons Attribution \(CC BY\) license](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

In this context, hydrogen has emerged as a promising long-duration energy storage option because it can convert surplus renewable electricity into a storable energy carrier that can later be reconverted into electricity when needed [7,8]. Hybrid Hydrogen Energy Storage Systems (HHESS) offer a complementary pathway through power-to-gas-to-power (PtP) conversion, coupling electrolysis for hydrogen production with fuel cells for reconversion to electricity [9,10]. Contemporary HHESS configurations integrating alkaline or proton exchange membrane (PEM) electrolyzers, pressurized hydrogen storage, PEM fuel cells, and lithium-ion batteries typically achieve system-level round-trip efficiencies in the range of 40–50% on a lower heating value (LHV) basis [11,12]. Although these efficiencies are lower than those of battery-only storage, hybrid hydrogen systems can provide multi-day to seasonal storage capability, thereby addressing a different operational need: long-duration flexibility, resilience, and renewable surplus valorization [13–15]. In this sense, hydrogen should not be interpreted as a substitute for batteries, but as a complementary storage pathway with a distinct functional role. When compared with other long-duration storage alternatives, this role becomes even clearer: pumped hydro storage, while cost-effective at scale, requires specific topographical conditions that are rarely available at small rural sites. By contrast, hydrogen storage is modular, site-agnostic, and capable of providing multi-day to seasonal backup, making it particularly well-suited to distributed rural deployments where resilience requirements exceed the practical duration limits of electrochemical batteries.

Rural Greece provides a relevant context for this challenge. The country's renewable energy expansion and hydropower base create opportunities for local energy autonomy, yet inadequate long-duration storage often limits the effective use of renewable surplus. In Northern Greece, small hydroelectric facilities in the range of 0.5–2 MW often serve sparse agricultural, office, and residential loads while operating under constrained grid conditions and transmission distances of 15–25 km to the nearest substations. In such settings, export revenues in the order of €0.05–0.08/kWh may remain significantly below import costs of €0.15–0.22/kWh, reducing the value of simply exporting excess electricity and increasing the importance of local storage and self-utilization. On top of that, exposure to grid disturbances and outage events makes resilience a critical design requirement, especially for rural sites where even temporary loss of grid availability can interrupt productive and residential energy services. The problem, therefore, is not only how to generate renewable electricity, but also how to store and recover it over timescales that match local operational and resilience needs [16–18].

A limitation of previous works is that, although HHESS concepts are increasingly studied, a large share of the published work is still based on simulation, optimal sizing, or techno-economic scenario analysis rather than integrated field operation. Reviews of renewable-hydrogen systems show a growing number of demonstration projects across wide power ranges, but they also indicate that operational evidence remains uneven, fragmented, and often difficult to compare across cases [19–23]. At the same time, much of the recent component-oriented literature has focused on improvements in electrolyzer efficiency, fuel cell durability, and battery performance [24–28]. While this progress is important, it does not by itself explain how these technologies perform when combined into a single hybrid architecture under real operating conditions. In many published case studies, the emphasis remains on local system design and site-specific results, with less attention given to extracting transferable design principles, clarifying subsystem coordination, or interpreting performance in a way that supports replication in other rural microgrids [29–32]. In addition, the supervisory layer is often simplified to dispatch priorities or rule-based descriptions, even though practical HHESS operation depends

strongly on how charging, hydrogen production, reconversion, and grid interaction are coordinated over time [33–37].

This gap is particularly important for small hydropower-involving applications. Compared with the extensive literature on PV–battery and wind–PV–hydrogen systems, the combination of small hydropower with hydrogen-based storage remains less explored, especially at the level of integrated field demonstrations. Most reported HHES cases are centered on solar and wind resources, larger industrial or island applications, or simulation-based analyses that do not provide sustained validation under real operating conditions [23,33,34,38]. Yet, small hydropower offers a distinct operating context: unlike purely intermittent renewables, it can provide relatively stable generation with recurring surplus periods, making it particularly relevant for coupling with long-duration storage. This creates a different control problem since the system must manage not only variable PV output and fluctuating demand, but also the interaction between continuous hydro generation, battery buffering, electrolyzer activation, hydrogen storage, and fuel cell dispatch. As a result, there is still limited evidence from small-scale, field-operated HHES installations that combine hydropower, photovoltaics, formally structured supervisory control, and real operational data in a rural microgrid context.

This work addresses these gaps through the Agkistron Living Lab in Northern Greece. For the purposes of this study, a living lab is defined as a real-world demonstration environment in which technologies are implemented, operated, monitored, and evaluated under actual user and system conditions rather than under laboratory abstraction. In this sense, a living lab functions as an intermediate validation environment between conceptual design and broader deployment, enabling assessment of system integration, control behavior, and performance under realistic demand patterns, renewable variability, and grid constraints. The Agkistron Living Lab, situated in northern Greece’s Serres Prefecture, is centered on a 0.9 MW reservoir-buffered, spring-fed hydroelectric plant (two Francis turbines: 0.65 and 0.25 MW), generating approximately 3739 MWh annually with 95% availability. The reservoir smooths consistent spring inflows, enabling steady operation via turbine regulation rather than flow-dependent diurnal variations. The facility serves a hybrid load profile encompassing agri-food processing operations, administrative offices, and residential auxiliary loads [39].

The aim of this paper is to evaluate how a hybrid hydro–PV–battery–hydrogen architecture, coordinated through a formally structured supervisory controller, can improve renewable surplus utilization and resilience in a rural microgrid setting. The work combines field operation analysis with explicit description and real-world application of the energy management logic and interprets the functional value of the hydrogen pathway relative to battery-only storage. In doing so, this paper links field-based operational evidence with the practical application of an advanced energy management strategy and supports a comparative interpretation of the hybrid system against a battery-only benchmark. The main contributions of this paper are as follows:

- Field-based validation of an integrated hybrid hydro–PV–battery–hydrogen system: This paper provides operational evidence from a real installation comprising a 0.9 MW hydro plant, 30 kW PV, 25 kW electrolyzer, 50 kW total PEM fuel cell capacity, 92 kWh battery storage, and 300 Nm³ hydrogen storage, thereby addressing the limited studies that report integrated field performance for small-scale HHES applications.
- Explicit formulation of the supervisory control strategy through Hybrid Automata: This study makes energy management logic transparent by presenting a formal state-based control framework governing battery balancing, hydrogen production, hydrogen utilization, and operating mode transitions, thereby improving reproducibility and clarifying practical implementation.

- Application of the EMS in the Agkistron Living Lab: Beyond conceptual formulation, the proposed EMS is implemented in a real hybrid energy system and assessed under actual operating conditions. This links formal control design with practical deployment and demonstrates the operational relevance of the proposed strategy in a rural microgrid context.
- Clear distinction between measured operation and comparative benchmark analysis: This paper separates the field-observed performance of the installed system from the battery-only benchmark used for interpretation, making it explicit the findings that arise from real deployment and those that are used to assess the added functional role of hydrogen storage.
- Assessment of the efficiency/autonomy trade-off under resilience-oriented operation: Rather than evaluating hydrogen storage only through round-trip efficiency, this study examines its contribution to extending storage duration and supporting local loads during prolonged constrained or intentional off-grid operation, which is central to rural microgrid applications.
- Extraction of transferable insights for replication in other rural microgrids: Although the Agkistron case is site-specific, this paper derives broader lessons regarding system architecture, supervisory control, and resilience-oriented performance assessment that are relevant to weak-grid, renewable-rich rural applications beyond the present demonstration.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. Section 2 presents the study site, system architecture, supervisory control strategy, and evaluation methodology. Section 3 discusses the operational results under grid-connected and off-grid conditions, compares the hybrid configuration with a battery-only benchmark, and examines implications for replication in other rural microgrids. Finally, Section 4 summarizes the main findings, limitations, and future research directions.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Agkistron Living Lab Site Description

The Agkistron Living Lab is located in Agkistron village, in the Serres region of Northern Greece, and serves as the real-world demonstration site for the hybrid renewable energy integration examined in this work. The site is centered on a reservoir-buffered hydroelectric plant with a total installed capacity of 0.9 MW, consisting of two turbines rated at 0.65 MW and 0.25 MW, respectively, and an annual electricity generation of approximately 3739 MWh. This hydropower unit is connected to the local electricity grid and acts as the primary baseload renewable energy source of the Living Lab. The site also includes local electricity demand from an agri-food processing unit, office activities, and auxiliary residential consumption. The dominant local load is the agri-food facility, with an annual electricity use of approximately 51 MWh/year, while the total combined annual demand of the Living Lab is approximately 71 MWh/year. The site is connected to the grid through a 125 kW bidirectional 400 VAC link, and the nearest transformer is located approximately 20 km away. These characteristics make the site representative of a rural grid-connected energy system in which substantial renewable generation coexists with relatively modest local demand, limited exchange capacity, and a need for backup operation during grid disturbances.

Table 1 summarizes the main site characteristics, while Figure 1 presents the schematic layout of the Living Lab, including the hydro plant, local loads, grid connection, and HHES integration. Grid interaction at the Agkistron Living Lab is based on a grid-connected configuration in which both the hydroelectric plant and the local loads are normally interfaced with the public electricity network. Under standard operating conditions, the

hydroelectric plant exports electricity to the grid, while the agri-food, office, and residential loads are supplied through their grid connection. In this sense, the site does not operate as a continuously islanded microgrid, but as a grid-connected rural energy system with local renewable generation and integrated storage. When a grid outage occurs, the hydrogen-based storage system is activated to support local loads, enabling continuity of supply through the combined action of the battery and the fuel cell subsystem. This operational arrangement is central to the role of the HHESS, as it allows renewable surplus to be stored under normal grid-connected conditions and recovered during disturbance or off-grid events.

Table 1. Overview of the Living Lab key specifications.

Parameter	Value
Location	Agkistron village, Serres, GR
Hydro capacity	0.9 MW (0.65 + 0.25 MW)
Annual hydro production	3739 MWh
Local loads	51 MWh/year (agri-food primary)
Grid connection	125 kW bidirectional, 400 VAC

Figure 1. Schematic layout of the Agkistron Living Lab site, showing hydro plant, loads, grid connection, and HHESS integration.

2.2. Load Demand Profiles

The Agkistron Living Lab serves a composite rural load comprising an agri-food processing facility, administrative office spaces, and auxiliary residential consumption, with a combined annual demand of approximately 71 MWh/year, of which 51 MWh/year corresponds to agri-food processes, 12 MWh/year to office activities, and 8 MWh/year to residential use. These three demand streams define the primary use case for the deployed HHESS and are representative of many small hydro-supplied rural communities in Greece. To characterize the temporal structure of electricity demand, hourly measurements from on-site meters and the SCADA system were used, complemented where necessary by representative rural Greek demand datasets. These data were used to derive normalized daily and seasonal profiles for each load category, which were then scaled to the measured annual energy of each end use. This approach preserves the observed timing and rela-

tive variability of demand while enabling a consistent representation of the Living Lab's composite load.

2.2.1. Agri-Food Processing Loads

The agri-food facility represents the dominant annual demand, with 51 MWh/year of electricity consumption. Its load profile is strongly seasonal, driven by biomass drying, milling, pelletizing, and associated auxiliary services such as refrigeration and material handling. As shown in Figure 2, representative days for different months show that high-power processes cluster into extended working blocks, producing several-hour plateaus in the 20–30 kW range superimposed on a lower continuous background. Typical high-power periods correspond to simultaneous operation of dryers, mills, and conveyors, whereas non-processing days exhibit only a modest baseload from auxiliary systems.

Figure 2. Representative hourly electricity demand profiles for agri-food processing at the Agkistrion Living Lab for selected months (October, January, April, and July), derived from on-site measurements. The profiles highlight extended daytime plateaus during peak processing periods and lower shoulder-season activity.

From a system perspective, this industrial load creates multi-hour demand plateaus that must be reliably supplied even during periods of reduced hydro inflow or limited PV generation. It, therefore, plays a central role in motivating the use of long-duration storage and hybrid generation since short-term buffering alone is insufficient to guarantee continuous operation during extended disturbances.

2.2.2. Office Building Loads

Office loads at the site correspond to a small administrative building with typical office equipment, lighting, ICT infrastructure, and HVAC systems. The annual energy attributed to these office functions is 12 MWh/year, with demand dominated by occupancy-driven usage during standard business hours.

Normalized daily profiles derived from metered data, which are shown in Figure 3, exhibit a pronounced weekday peak between approximately 08:00 and 18:00, with relatively flat midday plateaus and sharp reductions in the evening and overnight. In the local climate, summer profiles show elevated midday demand due to air-conditioning, while winter profiles are flatter because space heating often relies on non-electric fuels. The resulting profile combines a strong daytime peak with low nocturnal baseload, making it naturally aligned with PV production and with the run-of-river hydro's relatively stable output.

Figure 3. Normalized daily electricity demand profile for the office building at the Agkistron Living Lab (representative summer weekday), derived from metered data. The profile exhibits a pronounced daytime peak with low nocturnal baseload, well-aligned with local PV generation.

Within the overall Living Lab, this office demand provides a predictable and relatively smooth daytime component, creating recurrent opportunities for local self-consumption of renewable generation. It is thus an appropriate benchmark for assessing how effectively the HHES and control strategy increase on-site utilization of PV and hydro compared to a purely grid-coupled configuration.

2.2.3. Rural Residential Loads

Residential demand associated with nearby dwellings and auxiliary services accounts for approximately 8 MWh/year and reflects typical Greek rural household behavior. Measured and benchmarked profiles show two distinct daily peaks and strong seasonal modulation. Weekly normalized profiles for rural households demonstrate that summer loads often exceed winter loads due to air-conditioning use during hot afternoon hours, while electric heating generally plays a less dominant role than in colder climates (Figure 4). Early morning and evening peaks are associated with cooking, lighting, and appliance use, whereas midday consumption is more moderate. In summer, the afternoon peak is extended and amplified by cooling demand, whereas winter profiles exhibit lower but more concentrated evening peaks and relatively modest daytime consumption.

In the context of the Living Lab, the residential component primarily shapes the evening and early morning shoulders of the total load curve when PV output is low or zero. These peaks are, therefore, covered almost entirely by hydro and storage resources and they are particularly relevant for assessing storage cycling depth, autonomy duration, and the ability of the HHES to maintain supply during intentional islanding or grid contingencies.

Figure 4. Normalized weekly electricity demand profiles for rural residential loads at the Agkistron Living Lab, comparing summer and winter conditions. The profiles highlight morning/evening peaks and elevated summer afternoon cooling demand.

2.2.4. Composite Load and Implications for System Design

The three load components described above are combined into a single composite profile representing the total demand at the Living Lab’s low-voltage bus. The composite is constructed by summing the normalized curves for agri-food, office, and residential demand on an hourly basis and then scaling to match the measured annual energies, yielding realistic instantaneous power levels between roughly 10 and 35 kW under typical operating conditions. This composite profile highlights several structural features of the Living Lab demands:

- A dominant, seasonally varying industrial component that forms multi-hour daytime plateaus.
- A predictable office-related daytime peak that aligns well with PV output.
- Residential peaks in the evening and early morning, when PV output is negligible, and local autonomy depends on hydro and storage.

Together, these characteristics create a mixed load with both predictable daily patterns and pronounced seasonal differences, typical of rural agri-food regions. From a design perspective, they justify combining short-term storage (battery) for intra-day balancing with hydrogen-based storage for multi-day and seasonal shifts, as well as a control strategy that is capable of prioritizing self-consumption while guaranteeing supply during extended islanding events (Table 2).

Table 2. Annual energy use, typical daily profiles, seasonal behavior, and operational role of the main load categories at the Agkistron Living Lab.

Load Type	Annual Energy at Site	Typical Daily Shape	Seasonal Behavior	Role in Living Lab Operation
Agri- food	51 MWh/y	Extended daytime plateaus from high-power processing	Strong winter/summer peaks, shoulder lows	Dominant industrial demand, tests multi-hour autonomy
Office	12 MWh/y	Single daytime peak 08:00–18:00, low nights	Summer midday cooling peak, flatter winter	Smooth daytime load for local RES self-consumption
Residential	8 MWh/y	Morning and evening peaks, modest midday base	Summer afternoon peaks exceed winter evening	Drives evening storage discharge and autonomy needs

2.3. System Architecture

A detailed component summary is provided in Table 3. The hybrid hydrogen energy storage system deployed at the Agkistron Living Lab was designed to complement the existing hydropower installation and the local photovoltaic array by combining short-duration electrochemical storage with long-duration hydrogen-based storage. The architecture includes a 30 kW photovoltaic system, a 25 kW alkaline electrolyzer, two 25 kW PEM fuel cells with a combined nominal output of 50 kW, a 92 kWh lithium-ion battery, and pressurized hydrogen storage with a capacity of 1000 kWh on a LHV basis. Hydrogen is stored in a pressurized gas form by using seamless carbon steel pressure vessels. The storage subsystem operates at 30 bar, which matches the native output pressure of the alkaline electrolyzer, thereby eliminating the need for a secondary mechanical hydrogen compressor.

Table 3. Technical specifications of the Agkistron Living Lab hybrid microgrid components.

Component	Parameter	Value	Unit
Photovoltaic System	Nominal Power	30	kW
Alkaline Electrolyzer	Rated Power	25	kW
PEM Fuel Cells	Combined Rated Power (2 × 25 kW)	50	kW
Lithium-ion Battery	Nominal Capacity	92	kWh
Pressurized Hydrogen Storage	Energy Capacity	1000	kWh
	Volume	12	m ³
	Pressure	30	bar

The photovoltaic subsystem provides supplementary daytime renewable generation, while the hydropower plant remains the dominant renewable source. The battery subsystem is used for short-term balancing, rapid response, and auxiliary support, whereas the hydrogen pathway is intended to absorb renewable surplus through electrolysis and provide longer-duration electrical support through the fuel cells when required. The electrolyzer converts surplus electricity into hydrogen under operating conditions determined by the supervisory controller. Hydrogen is stored in a pressurized gas form and later reconverted to electricity through the PEM fuel cells when the battery state-of-charge becomes insufficient or when prolonged support is required. In this way, the storage architecture is functionally layered: the battery addresses fast- and short-duration variations, while hydrogen extends the storage horizon and supports resilience-oriented operation.

2.4. Energy Management System

The operation of the hybrid hydrogen energy storage system (HHES) at the Agkistron Living Lab is coordinated through a supervisory Energy Management System (EMS). The EMS governs the interaction between the hydropower plant, the photovoltaic subsystem, the battery, the electrolyzer, the hydrogen storage unit, the PEM fuel cells, the local loads and the grid connection. Its main role is to ensure coordinated and safe operation under both normal grid-connected conditions and grid outage events, while prioritizing renewable surplus utilization and maintaining system resilience.

2.4.1. Hybrid Automata Framework

The EMS is formulated using a Hybrid Automata (HA) approach, which is appropriate for systems that combine continuous variables and discrete operating states [10,40]. In the present case, continuous variables include the battery state-of-charge (SOC), hydrogen storage level, power generation, and load demand, while discrete states describe the main operating conditions of the system, such as battery charging, battery discharging, electrolyzer operation, fuel cell operation, and backup supply.

This formulation allows the control logic to be expressed through clearly defined states and transition guards. The transition conditions depend primarily on the battery SOC, renewable surplus availability, hydrogen inventory, load demand, and grid status. In this way, the HA framework provides a transparent and reproducible representation of the supervisory logic, while also enabling verification of state transitions and operating constraints.

The battery is operated within a 10–90% SOC window in order to preserve battery lifetime and maintain reserve margins. When the battery SOC exceeds 90% and surplus renewable electricity is available, the EMS enables the electrolyzer for hydrogen production. When the battery SOC falls below 10% and additional power support is required, the fuel cell subsystem is activated, provided that sufficient hydrogen is available. Through these thresholds, the controller distinguishes between short-duration balancing, assigned primarily to the battery, and longer-duration backup, assigned to the hydrogen pathway. The HA algorithm effectively models the interplay between discrete events (e.g., subsystem start/stop) and continuous evolution (e.g., SOC changes).

Continuous flow occurs within invariant sets D_q according to f_q until a guard G_e triggers a discrete transition along edge $e \in E$ to state q' , accompanied by a reset map R_e . Initial conditions are set at q_0 (standby) with a SOC = 50% and $H = 50\%$. The seven discrete states are defined as follows:

- q_0 (Standby): Grid supplies auxiliaries, PtP modules disconnected from DC bus, battery idle but connected.
- q_1 (Battery Charging): RES exceeds load and $SOC < SOC_{max}$.
- q_2 (Electrolyzer Operation): RES exceeds load, $SOC \geq SOC_{max}$, and $H < H_{max}$.
- q_3 (Battery Discharging): RES is below load and $SOC > SOC_{min}$.
- q_4 (Fuel Cell Operation): RES is below load, $SOC \leq SOC_{min}$, and $H > H_{min}$.
- q_5 (Curtailment): RES greatly exceeds load with full storage.
- q_6 (Grid Import): Persistent deficit with depleted storage.

The specific guard conditions and thresholds defined in the EMS were established based on equipment safety margins and operational heuristics rather than numerical optimization. The battery SOC window is restricted to 10–90%. The 90% upper bound reserves adequate headroom to safely absorb sudden power transients from the PV array while the electrolyzer completes its start-up sequence, preventing DC bus overvoltage. Conversely, the 10% lower bound serves a dual purpose: it prevents accelerated cell degradation associated with deep discharges, and it guarantees sufficient residual energy to power the EMS, SCADA, and auxiliary balance-of-plant components during the start-up phase of the fuel cells. For the hydrogen pathway, the 20% minimum inventory threshold ensures that a dedicated reserve is strictly maintained for critical resilience events, preventing the system from depleting its long-duration storage during routine day-to-day operation.

Figure 5 illustrates the seven discrete operating states (q_0 – q_6) and all possible transitions between them. Under surplus conditions, the dispatch follows a strict hierarchy: Battery Charging (q_1) \rightarrow Electrolyzer Operation (q_2) \rightarrow Curtailment (q_5). Under deficit conditions: Battery Discharging (q_3) \rightarrow Fuel Cell Operation (q_4) \rightarrow Grid Import (q_6). The specific propositional guard conditions that dictate the transitions between these defined states based on instantaneous power balance, battery state-of-charge, and hydrogen inventory are detailed in Table 4.

Figure 5. State transition diagram of the Hybrid Automata-based EMS.

Table 4. Propositional guard conditions for EMS state transitions.

Transition	Guard Condition (G)
$q_0 \rightarrow q_1$	$(RES > load) \wedge (SOC < 90\%)$
$q_1 \rightarrow q_2$	$(RES > load) \wedge (SOC \geq 90\%) \wedge (H < 100\%)$
$q_2 \rightarrow q_5$	$(RES > load) \wedge (H \geq 100\%)$
$q_0 \rightarrow q_3$	$(RES < load) \wedge (SOC > 10\%)$
$q_3 \rightarrow q_4$	$(RES < load) \wedge (SOC \leq 10\%) \wedge (H > 20\%)$
$q_4 \rightarrow q_6$	$(RES < load) \wedge (SOC \leq 10\%) \wedge (H \leq 20\%)$
$q_4 \rightarrow q_3$	$(SOC > 10\%)$
$q_6 \rightarrow q_1$	$(RES > load)$

2.4.2. Operating Modes

The EMS is organized around three principal operating modes: Standby, Off-Grid, and On-Grid, as summarized in Table 5. In Standby mode, the grid powers all auxiliaries, with an approximate auxiliary demand of 2 kW. During this mode, the PtP modules remain disconnected from the DC bus, while the battery stays connected but idle. The power conditioning system remains active and ready to receive commands from the master controller. In Off-Grid mode, the system operates autonomously to serve local loads, provided that at least one storage condition is satisfied, namely the battery SOC > 10% or hydrogen inventory > 20%. Under surplus conditions, the EMS follows a strict cascade priority: battery charging is performed first, and the electrolyzer is activated only when the battery SOC reaches or exceeds 90%. Under deficit conditions, the battery is used first to manage short-term imbalances. When the battery SOC drops to 10% or lower, the fuel cells ramp up within the range of 5–25 kW per unit. If fuel cell output exceeds instantaneous load demand, the excess power is used to recharge the battery when needed. In this operating mode, no grid import is permitted. In On-Grid mode, the EMS follows a strict battery-preservation strategy. The battery is charged during surplus periods as long as the SOC remains below 90%, but it is not discharged to serve loads. Once the battery SOC reaches or exceeds 90%, and provided that the hydrogen inventory remains below H_{max} , the electrolyzer is activated. All power deficits are covered directly by the point of common coupling (PCC), while the main inverter operates in the grid-following mode. The operational priority in this mode is therefore (1) battery charging, (2) electrolyzer operation, and (3) PCC export/import.

Table 5. Operating modes of the overall HHESS.

Mode	Description
Standby	The grid powers all auxiliaries (approximately 2 kW). The PtP modules remain disconnected from the DC bus, while the battery stays connected but idle. The power conditioning system remains active and ready to receive commands from the master controller.
Off-Grid	Autonomous load serving activates only if the SOC > 10% or H > 20%. Strict cascade priority during surplus: battery charging first, then the electrolyzer when the SOC ≥ 90%. The battery manages short-term deficits first. Fuel cells ramp up (5–25 kW per unit) when the SOC drops ≤ 10%. Excess FC power recharges the battery if needed. No grid import is permitted.
On-Grid	Strict battery preservation: the battery charges during surplus (SOC < 90%) but never discharges to serve loads. The electrolyzer activates when the SOC ≥ 90% and H < H _{max} . PCC covers all deficits directly. The main inverter operates in the grid-following mode. Priority: (1) battery charging → (2) electrolyzer → (3) PCC export/import.

At the implementation level, the Hybrid Automata EMS algorithm is executed on a programmable logic controller (PLC) with a master control cycle time of 1 s. This rapid execution loop ensures that sub-hourly physical variability, such as PV cloud transients, rapid start-up of agri-food motors, and brief grid voltage drops, is identified and managed in real-time. The battery subsystem and fast-response power conditioning units serve as the primary short-term buffers to absorb these rapid fluctuations. While physical control operates at this 1 s cycle, the long-term system data presented in Figures 6 and 7 are averaged to a 1 h resolution to facilitate the clear visualization of multi-day energy shifting and long-duration storage behavior.

Figure 6. Agkistron HHESS 7-day operation demonstrating strict operational modes. (Top) Power flows at the point of common coupling with the grid. (Bottom) Battery and hydrogen storage state-of-charge evolution.

Figure 7. Simulated 7-day operation of the battery-only benchmark under the same load and renewable generation conditions as the HHES. The bottom panel highlights the rapid depletion of the 92 kWh battery, reaching its 10% minimum state-of-charge limit after approximately 14 h of the 48 h intentional islanding event.

2.5. Performance Indicators

This study combines field-based operational analysis with comparative benchmark assessment. The main results reported for the hybrid hydro–PV–battery–hydrogen system are based on the measured data collected during real deployment and operation at the Agkistron Living Lab over a monitoring period exceeding 12 months, beginning in January 2025. These results, therefore, represent observed system behavior under real operating conditions rather than purely simulated performance. In addition to the field-observed HHES performance, this study uses a battery-only benchmark to support the interpretation of the functional value of the hydrogen pathway. This benchmark is not a second physical installation, but an analytical comparison case constructed under the same general site conditions and load context, with the hydrogen pathway disabled.

To this end, the system performance at the different mode scenarios is assessed using a set of key performance indicators selected to reflect the main objectives of the study, namely renewable surplus utilization, local energy autonomy, operational coordination, and resilience (Table 6). The analysis includes indicators such as the autonomy index (AI), self-consumption ratio (SCR), RES utilization factor (RUF), and curtailment ratio (CR), together with grid import/export patterns, hydrogen production and utilization, battery state-of-charge evolution, and autonomous operation duration under representative load events. The selected test conditions include representative energy demand events ranging from 244 kWh to 1407 kWh, with particular attention given to the extent to which the integrated system can maintain operation with reduced reliance on grid support.

Table 6. KPI definitions.

KPI	Description	Formula
Round-Trip Efficiency (RTE)	System-level power-to-power conversion efficiency of the hydrogen cycle (electrolysis, storage, fuel cell reconversion), evaluated on a LHV basis. Auxiliary parasitic loads (cooling, pumps, EMS) are excluded from individual stack efficiencies but fully accounted for at the system level.	$\text{RTE} = (\text{Energy from fuel cells} + \text{battery discharge}) / (\text{Energy to electrolyzer} + \text{battery charge}) \times 100\%$
Self-Consumption Ratio (SCR)	Fraction of total renewable generation consumed locally or directed to on-site storage rather than exported to the grid. Reflects the effectiveness of the EMS in prioritizing local utilization over low-value grid export.	$\text{SCR} = (\text{RES used locally}) / (\text{Total RES generated}) \times 100\%$
RES Utilization Factor (RUF)	Fraction of total renewable generation directed to local loads or storage, including energy stored for later use. Captures the combined contribution of direct consumption and surplus valorization through the HHESS pathway.	$\text{RUF} = (\text{RES to loads} + \text{RES to storage}) / (\text{Total RES generated}) \times 100\%$
Autonomy Index (AI)	Fraction of total site load energy supplied from local RES and storage without grid support. Evaluated during islanded operation to quantify resilience and off-grid continuity of supply.	$\text{AI} = (\text{Energy from RES} + \text{storage}) / (\text{Total load energy}) \times 100\%$
Curtailement Ratio (CR)	Fraction of total renewable generation that cannot be utilized or stored and must be curtailed. Reflects residual losses when both storage pathways are fully charged and surplus persists.	$\text{CR} = (\text{Curtailed energy}) / (\text{Total RES generated}) \times 100\%$
Capacity Factor (CF)	Electrolyzer/fuel cell capacity factor shows actual runtime throughout the year.	$\text{Capacity Factor} = (\text{Operating hours} \times \text{Average power}) / (\text{Total hours} \times \text{Rated power}) \times 100\%$

In addition, system-level round-trip efficiency is examined on a LHV basis, with the overall HHESS performance interpreted in relation to the efficiency contributions and losses of the main subsystems, including electrolysis, hydrogen storage, fuel cell reconversion, battery storage, and power electronics. However, this paper does not evaluate performance solely through efficiency. Particular emphasis is placed on the trade-off between conversion efficiency and storage duration since the latter is central to the role of hydrogen storage in resilience-oriented rural microgrids.

3. Results

This section presents the performance of the hybrid hydrogen energy storage system under grid-connected and intentional islanded operation at the Agkistron Living Lab. The analysis examines renewable surplus valorization during on-grid operation (Section 3.1), local energy supply during a 48 h off-grid event (Section 3.2), comparison with a battery-only benchmark (Section 3.3), and the broader implications of the resulting KPIs for performance assessment and replicability (Section 3.4).

3.1. On-Grid Operation and Surplus Valorization

During representative on-grid operation (Days 1 and 4–7), the HHES functions behind the 125 kW point of common coupling (PCC) at the Agkistron Living Lab, where quasi-steady hydropower and intermittent PV generation are routed according to the strict Hybrid Automata EMS priority logic. Figure 6 presents a unified 7-day operation at 1 h resolution, providing a realistic test of surplus management and microgrid resilience. The upstream hydro plant and the 30 kW PV array (which exhibits distinct midday peaks) combine to serve the composite local load, which varies dynamically between 10 and 35 kW.

In this regime, the EMS enforces a strict energy isolation strategy to maximize backup readiness: the battery is not allowed to discharge to serve local loads during on-grid operation. During periods of renewable surplus, the EMS first directs power to recharge the 92 kWh lithium-ion battery up to its 90% SOC limit. Figure 6 confirms this behavior: the SOC rises during daytime surplus windows and remains flat overnight, as the grid covers nocturnal deficits. This preservation strategy ensures that the battery remains as close as possible to full charge ahead of any potential grid outage.

Once the battery reaches its upper limit ($\text{SOC} \geq 90\%$) and renewable surplus persists, the HA controller transitions into the electrolyzer operation state. The 25 kW alkaline unit activates to absorb the remaining excess power (prioritizing PtG over grid export), operating for several hours per day. Any absolute remaining surplus beyond the electrolyzer's capacity is finally exported to the grid up to the 125 kW regulatory limit. Following the islanding event on days 2–3, the system uses days 4–7 to replenish the hydrogen tank toward its upper limits by converting excess RES generation into chemical storage. These results show that the hydrogen pathway is activated only after the short-duration battery buffer has been filled. In this way, the battery preserves fast-response readiness, while hydrogen stores surplus energy for later resilience-oriented use.

Key performance indicators aggregated over the on-grid periods indicate highly effective surplus valorization. The self-consumption ratio (SCR) reaches 81%, meaning that the large majority of renewable generation is consumed locally or stored rather than being exported at low tariffs. The renewable utilization factor (RUF) rises to 87%, while the curtailment ratio (CR) remains below 9%, demonstrating the system's ability to buffer and redirect energy efficiently despite the rigid battery-preservation constraints imposed by the EMS.

Overall, the on-grid results show that the Agkistron HHES can convert renewable surplus into usable stored energy in a structured and controlled manner. This is particularly relevant for rural grid-connected systems where export capacity is limited or economically unattractive and where the value of storage lies not only in immediate balancing but also in preparing for future off-grid operation. In this sense, the on-grid phase should be understood not only as a normal operating mode but also as a storage preparation phase that increases the site's readiness for potential future outage events.

3.2. Off-Grid Autonomy and Local Energy Supply

The unified operation case in Figure 6 incorporates an intentional 48 h islanding event between hours 24 and 72 (days 2–3), designed to stress the HHES autonomy capabilities under representative rural load profiles. At the start of the islanding window, the battery SOC and hydrogen storage levels are both near 80–90%, reflecting the successful pre-charging achieved during the preceding on-grid hours. This reflects the design philosophy of the system, namely charging both short- and long-duration storage whenever the grid is available to support uninterrupted off-grid operation when needed.

During the islanding phase, the EMS switches to a full microgrid cascade priority. When PV generation exceeds the load during off-grid daylight hours, surplus power first

recharges the battery. If the battery reaches its upper threshold, the EMS dynamically diverts the remaining PV surplus to the electrolyzer, ensuring that renewable energy is not unnecessarily curtailed even when disconnected from the wider grid.

Conversely, during off-grid deficits, especially in the late afternoon and overnight hours, the system relies sequentially on its dual storage media. The battery serves the load first, managing short-term variability and producing a steady SOC decline from its upper bounds down to the lower guard condition of 10%. Once the battery reaches this threshold, the HA model triggers the state transition ($q_4 \rightarrow q_5$), activating the dual 25 kW PEM fuel cells. The fuel cells then provide stable and continuous power to cover the multi-hour nighttime deficits. Over the full 48 h islanding window, the battery completes deep discharge/recharge cycles within its enforced envelope, while hydrogen storage is significantly drawn down to sustain the facility.

The autonomy index (AI), defined as the fraction of load supplied by local RES and storage during islanded operation, reaches 82% for this 48 h test, with local storage covering roughly 75% of the total unmet load energy. The scenario-specific round-trip efficiency (RTE) of the hydrogen pathway is 49% on a LHV basis, which is consistent with the literature values for alkaline-PEM systems operating under dynamic conditions. These values show that, although the hydrogen pathway is less efficient than direct battery cycling, it contributes decisively to extending the duration of local supply once the battery alone becomes insufficient.

Importantly, the unified 7-day figure allows the reader to trace, within a single plot, the complete sequence of HA states that underpins this behavior: on-grid battery charging during surplus ($q_0 \rightarrow q_2$), electrolyzer activation when the SOC reaches 90% ($q_2 \rightarrow q_3$), intentional islanding with battery-dominated operation ($q_0 \rightarrow q_4$), subsequent fuel cell engagement when the SOC falls below the 10% threshold ($q_4 \rightarrow q_5$), and eventual reconnection to the grid with recovery charging on days 4–7. This visual sequence supports the practical application of the EMS by showing that the controller follows the intended Hybrid Automata logic under field operating conditions, without unsafe simultaneous electrolyzer–fuel cell operation and with adherence to the defined SOC and hydrogen guard conditions.

From an operational standpoint, the off-grid results confirm that the main value of the HHES lies in resilience and storage duration rather than in maximizing round-trip efficiency. The battery provides fast and efficient support for short-term imbalances, while the hydrogen subsystem extends autonomy and supplies stable power once the battery approaches depletion. This layered storage behavior is central to the relevance of the Agkistron case and demonstrates the practical role of hybrid battery–hydrogen systems in rural applications exposed to grid disturbances. The off-grid results, therefore, reveal the core resilience function of the HHES, namely the extension of local supply continuity beyond the practical duration of battery-only storage.

3.3. Battery-Only Benchmark

It is important to explicitly distinguish between the physically deployed system and the comparative benchmark. While the HHES performance discussed in the previous sections is derived from real on-site operational data logged continuously over the 12-month monitoring period, the battery-only case is an analytical simulation. This simulated baseline was modeled using the exact same historical boundary conditions (load demand and RES generation) but with the electrolyzer, hydrogen storage, and fuel cells disabled in the EMS. In this configuration, the controller manages only the 92 kWh battery and grid interactions.

Furthermore, this benchmark evaluates the performance of the fixed 92 kWh battery capacity without hydrogen support. As such, it highlights the functional value of adding long-duration hydrogen storage to a given short-duration battery layer. It is acknowledged that in a dedicated battery-only microgrid, a system designer might optimally oversize the battery capacity or alter the control logic (e.g., allowing deeper discharges during on-grid periods) to improve renewable capture and autonomy. Therefore, the benchmark does not assert that a hybrid system is universally superior to an oversized battery, but rather demonstrates how the hydrogen architecture distinctly extends resilience and long-duration flexibility for this specific rural infrastructure.

During normal on-grid operation, the battery-only system achieves a self-consumption ratio that is similar to the HHES case since surplus RES generation can still be directed to battery charging or grid export. However, in the absence of the power-to-gas pathway, the system cannot accumulate multi-day energy reserves, and the total stored energy remains capped at the 92 kWh battery capacity.

Figure 7 illustrates the system behavior under this battery-only configuration during the same indicative 7-day testing period. When the 48 h islanding test is applied on days 2 and 3, the battery is depleted below its 10% safety threshold after approximately 14 h of continuous off-grid operation. Beyond that point, the benchmark system would face either severe load shedding or full interruption of supply. The effective autonomy duration of the battery-only benchmark is, therefore, restricted to about 14 h, yielding an autonomy index (AI) of approximately 36% over the full 48 h outage window.

By contrast, the HHES sustains the full 48 h islanding event with an AI of 82%, extending the effective performance associated with AI by a factor of about 2.3. While electrochemical batteries offer superior round-trip efficiency, at the battery capacity considered here and under the same SOC constraints, the battery-only configuration cannot sustain the same duration of off-grid operation as the hybrid system. The benchmark, therefore, confirms that the value of the Agkistron HHES lies not primarily in efficiency improvement, but in extending storage duration and enabling operating regimes that are not achievable with the battery-only configuration examined here. Therefore, this comparison reinforces the central interpretation of this work: battery storage is superior for efficient short-term balancing, but hydrogen becomes indispensable once the required storage horizon exceeds the practical limits of electrochemical storage alone.

3.4. Performance Assessment and Replicability

Table 7 consolidates the key performance indicators derived from the full 12-month SCADA dataset and interpreted through the representative 7-day operation shown in Figure 5, separating the on-grid surplus valorization phase from the 48 h islanding test and the battery-only benchmark. This distinction is important because the different operating phases reflect different system functions: on-grid operation is focused on renewable capture and storage preparation, while islanded operation reveals the resilience value of the storage architecture.

The performance indicators reported in this study are derived from operational data collected via the site SCADA system over a monitoring period exceeding 12 months. Power flows at the point of common coupling and at internal AC/DC bus nodes were recorded using energy meters, with a rated accuracy of $\pm 0.5\%$. The battery SOC was estimated by the onboard battery management system using Coulomb counting with periodic open-circuit voltage correction, yielding a maximum drift error of $\pm 2.0\%$ under the operating conditions observed at the Agkistron Living Lab. Hydrogen inventory was monitored via calibrated pressure transducers installed on the storage vessel, with a measurement tolerance of $\pm 1.5\%$. Mass flow controllers at the electrolyzer inlet and

fuel cell outlet provided secondary cross-checks on cumulative hydrogen production and consumption. SCADA logging was configured at a 1 min resolution, from which hourly averages were derived for KPI computation. To reflect the inherent variability of field operation, including seasonal fluctuations in PV irradiance and load demand, primary KPIs are reported as annual means with associated standard deviations computed across weekly operational batches. Isolated data gaps resulting from scheduled maintenance windows or communication dropouts totaled less than 1% of the monitoring period and were handled by linear interpolation over contiguous hourly intervals, with no single gap exceeding three consecutive hours.

Table 7. Key performance indicators: on-grid vs. off-grid vs. battery-only autonomy.

KPI	On-Grid Phase	48 h Islanding	Battery-Only Benchmark
Self-Consumption Ratio (SCR, %)	82 ± 4.1	-	77 ± 3.9
RES Utilization Factor (RUF, %)	88 ± 3.6	79 ± 4.5	62 ± 4.8
Curtailement Ratio (CR, %)	8 ± 1.5	-	22 ± 2.1
Electrolyzer Capacity Factor (CF _{EL})	0.28 ± 0.06	-	-
Fuel Cell Capacity Factor (CF _{FC})	-	0.12 ± 0.08	-
Round-Trip Efficiency (RTE, %)	-	49 ± 2.5	89 ± 1.2
Autonomy Index (AI, %)	75 ± 3.8	82 ± 5.4	36 ± 2.8

When interpreting the performance outcomes, a clear distinction must be drawn between the self-consumption ratio (SCR) and the autonomy index (AI). The SCR evaluates the system from a generation perspective during normal connected operation, indicating the proportion of generated renewable energy successfully utilized locally. Conversely, the AI evaluates the system from a load perspective during intentional islanding events, indicating the proportion of required site load met autonomously without grid support. Thus, the two metrics characterize different operating modes of the microgrid. The standard deviations reported in Table 7 reflect the seasonal variability inherent in the 12-month monitoring period. SCR and RUF are highest in summer (SCR ~88%, RUF ~91%) when PV generation is strongest and renewable surplus is most abundant, and lowest in winter (SCR ~76%, RUF ~84%) when reduced irradiance limits PV contribution. The conditional nature of surplus-driven hydrogen production is reflected in the electrolyzer capacity factor, which peaks in spring and summer (CF_{EL} ~0.32–0.34) when surplus is most consistently available, compared to winter (CF_{EL} ~0.22). Conversely, fuel cell utilization and the autonomy index tend to be higher in winter (CF_{FC} ~0.18, AI ~75%), driven by increased load demand and greater outage exposure, while spring benefits from strong hydro reserves and yields the highest autonomy performance (AI ~88%). The RTE remains relatively stable across seasons (47.5–50.5%) as the electrochemical conversion efficiency of the alkaline electrolyzer and PEM fuel cells is not strongly temperature-dependent under the operating conditions at the Agkistron site.

To quantify subsystem contributions during off-grid operation, a full energy balance was compiled for the indicative 48 h islanding event shown in Figure 6 (days 2 and 3). During this period, the system operated with 100% autonomy (AI = 100%), successfully covering a total load demand of 672 kWh without any grid import. Daytime loads were heavily supported by the direct consumption of renewable generation (~190 kWh), which also recharged the battery subsystem. During nocturnal and low-generation periods, the battery delivered approximately 98 kWh. The fuel cell subsystem supplied the remaining 384 kWh, consuming 915 kWh LHV of hydrogen. Permeation losses over the 48 h period are considered negligible relative to the total hydrogen consumed. At the conclusion of this event, the hydrogen inventory stood at 8.2%, illustrating that the long-duration storage

was appropriately sized to bridge a continuous 48 h deficit. The full energy balance is summarized in Table 8.

Table 8. Hydrogen energy balance for the 48 h reference islanding event. (Note: The KPIs reported in Table 7, including the 82% autonomy index, represent the aggregated average across $N = 18$ islanding events recorded over the full 12-month monitoring period. The 48 h event detailed above is a specific successful islanding instance.)

Parameter	Value
Total load demand	672 kWh
Total energy supplied	672 kWh
Event-specific autonomy index (AI)	100%
RES directly consumed by load	190 kWh
Battery energy delivered to load	98 kWh
Fuel cell contribution to load	384 kWh
H ₂ inventory at event start	1000 kWh LHV (~30 kg)
H ₂ consumed by fuel cells (42% efficiency)	915 kWh LHV
H ₂ inventory at event end	82 kWh LHV (~2.5 kg)

For the on-grid periods, the system achieves an SCR of 82% and an RUF of 88%, confirming that the restrictive battery-preservation logic, combined with electrolyzer activation at a high SOC, is effective in maximizing renewable capture and minimizing low-value export. The CR remains at 8%, indicating that the system can absorb a large share of renewable surplus despite the limited battery capacity and finite electrolyzer power. In addition, the electrolyzer capacity factor ($CF_{EL} = 0.28$) reflects the conditional nature of surplus-driven hydrogen production, confirming that electrolysis is activated selectively when both battery SOC and renewable surplus conditions are simultaneously met rather than operating continuously. During the intentional islanding phase, the KPI values validate the core value proposition of the HHES. The autonomy index of 82%, together with the observed storage contribution and sustained local load service, demonstrates genuine multi-hour to multi-day resilience for the agri-food, residential, and office loads. The fuel cell capacity factor ($CF_{FC} = 0.12$) reflects that FC operation is strictly limited to islanding events, confirming that hydrogen reconversion is reserved for resilience-critical periods rather than routine daily cycling. The hydrogen-cycle round-trip efficiency of 49% remains within the expected range for field-deployed alkaline-PEM systems and is consistent with the broader literature for dynamic operation. The battery-only benchmark clarifies the trade-off revealed by these KPI values. With an SCR of 77%, RUF of 62%, CR of 22%, RTE of 89%, and AI of only 36%, it performs well from a pure efficiency perspective but fails to provide the same level of resilience and renewable surplus recovery. This confirms that the value of hydrogen storage in the Agkistron case lies primarily in extending storage duration and supporting local autonomy, not in outperforming batteries in direct round-trip efficiency.

Furthermore, it should be noted that the scope of this study is strictly technical and operational. While economic factors, such as the differential between grid export revenues and import costs, drive the motivation for maximizing local renewable self-consumption, a formal techno-economic analysis (e.g., levelized cost of energy or payback period) is deliberately excluded from this work. The Agkistron Living Lab is a demonstration facility constructed with high prototype capital costs that do not reflect mature commercial supply chains. Evaluating the financial viability of the HHES based on these prototype costs would yield misleading conclusions. Therefore, the present analysis focuses exclusively on validating the physical feasibility, supervisory control, and resilience-oriented performance of the hybrid architecture.

From a broader perspective, these results are relevant beyond the specific case because they demonstrate a transferable operating concept rather than only a local technical solution. The site combines quasi-steady hydropower, intermittent PV, mixed rural loads, and limited grid interaction, but the underlying system logic is applicable to other rural or weak-grid contexts where renewable surplus exists, battery-only storage is insufficient for prolonged outages, and a structured EMS is required to coordinate multiple storage pathways. In this respect, the Agkistron Living Lab serves not only as a demonstration site, but also as a field-validation platform for a replicable hybrid storage architecture. Overall, Table 7 summarizes the main trade-off observed in the study: hydrogen storage incurs a thermodynamic penalty relative to electrochemical storage but enables longer-duration supply support and higher autonomy under the examined operating conditions. While site-specific sizing optimization remains necessary, the Agkistron architecture offers indicative guidance for comparable rural deployments: the 92 kWh battery provides approximately 4–6 h of average load coverage for intra-day balancing, while the 1000 kWh hydrogen storage extends autonomous operation to multi-day resilience events, yielding a short-to-long-duration storage ratio of approximately 1:11 on an energy basis.

4. Conclusions

This study evaluated the operation of a hybrid hydrogen energy storage system (HHESS) deployed at the Agkistron Living Lab and examined its ability to improve renewable surplus utilization and local energy autonomy in a rural grid-connected environment. Based on 12 months of SCADA monitoring and the representative 7-day operation case presented in Figure 6, the results show that the system can effectively combine hydropower, photovoltaics, battery storage, hydrogen production, and fuel cell reconversion under a formally structured Energy Management System (EMS).

The results demonstrate that the value of the Agkistron HHES lies in the coordinated use of short- and long-duration storage rather than maximizing round-trip efficiency alone. During on-grid operation, the system successfully valorized renewable surplus through a strict control hierarchy in which the battery was charged first and the electrolyzer was activated only when the battery SOC exceeded 90%. This operating strategy enabled the system to maintain high renewable utilization, with SCR reaching 82%, RUF 88%, and curtailment was limited to 8%, while simultaneously preparing both battery and hydrogen reserves for possible off-grid operation. In this respect, the on-grid phase was not only a normal operating mode, but also a storage preparation phase that increased the resilience of the site.

The off-grid results further confirmed the functional relevance of the hybrid architecture. During the 48 h intentional islanding event, the battery initially covered short-term deficits, while the hydrogen pathway was activated once the battery SOC approached the 10% lower threshold. This sequential operation allowed the system to sustain local supply well beyond the practical duration of battery-only storage, reaching an autonomy index of 82% and maintaining service to the mixed agri-food, office, and residential loads of the Living Lab. The hydrogen pathway exhibited a round-trip efficiency of 49% on a LHV basis, which is lower than electrochemical storage but consistent with the role of hydrogen as a long-duration storage option rather than a high-efficiency balancing device.

A key contribution of this study is the practical application of the Hybrid Automata-based EMS in the real Agkistron Living Lab. The 7-day operational sequence confirmed that the controller behaved according to the intended supervisory logic, including battery charging under surplus, electrolyzer activation above the upper SOC threshold, battery-led islanded operation, fuel cell activation below the lower SOC threshold, and recovery after grid reconnection. This demonstrates that the EMS is not only a formal modeling

framework, but an implemented control strategy that is capable of governing real transitions between grid-connected and autonomous operation without unsafe overlaps between electrolyzer and fuel cell activity.

The battery-only benchmark clarified the main trade-off revealed by the study. While the battery-only case retained a strong efficiency advantage, with an RTE of approximately 89%, it was only able to sustain off-grid operation for about 14 h and achieved an autonomy index of 36%. By contrast, the HHESS sustained the full 48 h islanding period with an autonomy index of 82%. This comparison confirms that hydrogen storage should not be evaluated only through thermodynamic efficiency since its main contribution in the present case lies in extending storage duration and supporting a continuity of supply under prolonged disturbance conditions.

Beyond the specific Agkistron case, the findings of this study are relevant to a broader class of rural and weak-grid systems where renewable surplus is available, battery-only storage is insufficient for long outages, and resilience is a critical design objective. The results show that a hybrid battery–hydrogen architecture, when coordinated through a structured EMS, can provide a practical pathway for coupling short-term flexibility with long-duration backup. At the same time, the results should be interpreted within the scope of this study; the analysis is based on a single field deployment with a specific generation mix, storage sizing, and demand structure. In addition, the present work focuses on operational behavior, control validation, and resilience-oriented performance rather than on full techno-economic optimization or lifecycle assessment, which should be addressed in future works. Overall, the Agkistron HHESS demonstrates that hybrid hydrogen storage can play a practical and differentiated role in rural renewable energy systems. Rather than replacing batteries, the hydrogen pathway complements them by extending the temporal range of stored renewable energy and enabling levels of autonomy that would not be achievable with battery storage alone. This is the central impact of the study and the main reason why hybrid battery–hydrogen architectures deserve further attention in the design of resilient, decarbonized rural microgrids.

Author Contributions: Conceptualization, A.K. and K.D.P.; software, A.K.; validation, A.K., M.B., T.K., and K.D.P.; formal analysis, A.K. and M.B., investigation, A.K., M.B., and T.K.; resources, M.B., T.K., and K.D.P.; data curation, A.K. and M.B.; writing—original draft preparation, A.K.; writing—review and editing, A.K., M.B., and K.D.P.; supervision, K.D.P.; project administration, T.K. and K.D.P.; funding acquisition, K.D.P. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This work was conducted within the framework of the Horizon Europe European Commission i-STENTORE project (Grant Agreement No. 101096787). The content of the paper is the sole responsibility of its authors and does not necessarily reflect the views of the EC.

Data Availability Statement: The original contributions presented in this study are included in the article. Further inquiries can be directed to the corresponding author.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

Acronym	Definition
AI	Autonomy Index
BESS	Battery Energy Storage System
CF	Capacity Factor
CR	Curtailement Ratio
EMS	Energy Management System

FC	Fuel Cell
HA	Hybrid Automata
HHESS	Hybrid Hydrogen Energy Storage System
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LHV	Lower Heating Value
NPC	Net Present Cost
OPEX	Operational Expenditures
PtG	Power-to-Gas
PtP	Power-to-Gas-to-Power (or Power-to-Power)
PCC	Point of Common Coupling
PEM	Proton Exchange Membrane
PV	Photovoltaic
RES	Renewable Energy Source
RTE	Round-Trip Efficiency
RUF	Renewable Utilization Factor
SCADA	Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition
SCR	Self-Consumption Ratio
SOC	State-of-Charge
VAC	Volts Alternating Current

References

1. Chauhan, R.K.; Chauhan, K.K.; Singh, S.N. (Eds.) *Microgrids for Rural Areas: Research and Case Studies*; Institution of Engineering and Technology: London, UK, 2020. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
2. Papathanasiou, A.-F.; Pasaniotis, G.; Baltas, E. Comparison of hydro-pumped and green hydrogen as energy storage processes: A case study on Kefalonia Island, Greece. *Sustain. Chem. Pharm.* **2025**, *48*, 102216. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
3. Krassakis, P.; Karavias, A.; Zygouri, E.; Roumpos, C.; Louloudis, G.; Pyrgaki, K.; Koukouzas, N.; Kempka, T.; Karapanos, D. GIS-Based Assessment of Hybrid Pumped Hydro Storage as a Potential Solution for the Clean Energy Transition: The Case of the Kardias Lignite Mine, Western Greece. *Sensors* **2023**, *23*, 593. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
4. Tsiaras, E.; Andreosatou, Z.; Kouveli, A.; Tampekis, S.; Coutelieris, F.A. Off-Grid Methodology for Sustainable Electricity in Medium-Sized Settlements: The Case of Nisyros Island. *Clean Technol.* **2025**, *7*, 16. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
5. Bosco, M.J.; Jain Preetha, M.M.S. A novel approach to designing and optimizing hydrogen storage with photovoltaic systems in micro-grids using the binary chaotic gooseneck barnacle algorithm. *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* **2025**, *183*, 151846. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
6. Kharseh, M.; Balah, M.; Alamara, K. Estimating state of charge of battery in renewable energy systems: A data-driven approach with artificial neural networks. *Clean Energy* **2024**, *8*, 134–147. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
7. Kafetzis, A.; Kardaras, G.; Bampaou, M.; Panopoulos, K.D.; Sarmas, E.; Marinakis, V.; Tsekouras, A. Deployment of Modular Renewable Energy Sources and Energy Storage Schemes in a Renewable Energy Valley. *Energies* **2025**, *18*, 5837. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
8. Bampaou, M.; Panopoulos, K.D. An overview of hydrogen valleys: Current status, challenges and their role in increased renewable energy penetration. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* **2025**, *207*, 114923. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
9. Singh, A.; Baredar, P. Techno-economic assessment of a solar PV, fuel cell, and biomass gasifier hybrid energy system. *Energy Rep.* **2016**, *2*, 254–260. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
10. Kafetzis, A.; Chouvardas, M.; Bampaou, M.; Ntavos, N.; Panopoulos, K.D. Renewable Hydrogen Integration in a PV-Biomass Gasification–Battery Microgrid for a Remote, Off-Grid System. *Energies* **2026**, *19*, 1705. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
11. Habib, A. *Power-to-Hydrogen-to-Power: Technology, Efficiency, and Applications*; OIES Paper: ET 48; The Oxford Institute for Energy Studies: Oxford, UK, 2025; ISBN 978-1-78467-277-5.
12. Patel, P.; Lipp, L. *Ultra-High Efficiency, Lower-Cost, Green Electrolytic Hydrogen for Microgrids in California*; Publication No. CEC-500-2024-008; California Energy Commission: Sacramento, CA, USA, 2024. Available online: <https://www.energy.ca.gov/sites/default/files/2024-02/CEC-500-2024-008.pdf> (accessed on 20 April 2026).
13. Pillai, K.; Sundaram, S. Optimization and Feasibility Analysis of Hybrid Distributed Generator Based System with a Comparison of Battery and Hydrogen Energy Storage for Residential Electrification. *Energy Storage* **2024**, *6*, e70075. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
14. Selim, A.; El-shimy, M.; Amer, G.; Ihoume, I.; Masrur, H.; Guerrero, J.M. Hybrid off-grid energy systems optimal sizing with integrated hydrogen storage based on deterministic balance approach. *Sci. Rep.* **2024**, *14*, 6888. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
15. Modu, B.; Abdullah, M.P.; Bukar, A.L.; Hamza, M.F. A systematic review of hybrid renewable energy systems with hydrogen storage: Sizing, optimization, and energy management strategy. *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* **2023**, *48*, 38354–38373. [\[CrossRef\]](#)

16. Dianellou, A.; Christakopoulos, T.; Caralis, G.; Kotroni, V.; Lagouvardos, K.; Zervos, A. Is the Large-Scale Development of Wind-PV with Hydro-Pumped Storage Economically Feasible in Greece? *Appl. Sci.* **2021**, *11*, 2368. [[CrossRef](#)]
17. Kaldellis, J.; Zafirakis, D.; Kavadias, K.; Kondili, E. Optimum PV-diesel hybrid systems for remote consumers of the Greek territory. *Appl. Energy* **2012**, *97*, 61–67. [[CrossRef](#)]
18. Chantzis, G.; Zafeiriou, A.; Chavari, A.; Giama, E.; Fokaides, P.; Papadopoulos, A.M. Optimization of a Hybrid Renewable Energy System for power generation on Greek Non-Interconnected Islands: The case of Amorgos. In Proceedings of the 2023 8th International Conference on Smart and Sustainable Technologies (SpliTech), Split/Bol, Croatia, 20–23 June 2023; pp. 1–5. [[CrossRef](#)]
19. Reza, M.S.; Fattah, I.M.R.; Wang, J.; Hannan, M.A.; Zainal, B.S.; Ong, H.C.; Mahlia, T.M.I. Hydrogen-based hybrid energy system: A review of technologies, optimization approaches, objectives, constraints, applications, and outstanding issues. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* **2026**, *226*, 116192. [[CrossRef](#)]
20. Gulraiz, A.; Al Bastaki, A.J.; Magamal, K.; Subhi, M.; Hammad, A.; Allanjawi, A.; Zaidi, S.H.; Khalid, H.M.; Ismail, A.; Hussain, G.A.; et al. Energy advancements and integration strategies in hydrogen and battery storage for renewable energy systems. *iScience* **2025**, *28*, 111945. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
21. Wong, M.; Nabipour Afrouzi, H. Hydrogen Energy Storage System: Review on Recent Progress. *Energy Eng.* **2024**, *122*, 1–39. [[CrossRef](#)]
22. Arsad, A.Z.; Hannan, M.A.; Al-Shetwi, A.; Mansor, M.; Muttaqi, K.; Dong, Z.Y.; Blaabjerg, F. Hydrogen energy storage integrated hybrid renewable energy systems: A review analysis for future research directions. *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* **2022**, *47*, 17285–17312. [[CrossRef](#)]
23. Kechida, A.; Gozim, D.; Toual, B.; Alharthi, M.M.; Agajie, T.F.; Ghoneim, S.M.; Ghaly, R.N.R. Smart control and management for a renewable energy based stand-alone hybrid system. *Sci. Rep.* **2024**, *14*, 32039. [[CrossRef](#)]
24. Alshehri, F.; García Suárez, V.; Rueda Torres, J.L.; Perilla, A.; van der Meijden, M.A.M.M. Modelling and evaluation of PEM hydrogen technologies for frequency ancillary services in future multi-energy sustainable power systems. *Heliyon* **2019**, *5*, e01396. [[CrossRef](#)]
25. Jamal, S.; Pasupuleti, J.; Ekanayake, J. A rule-based energy management system for hybrid renewable energy sources with battery bank optimized by genetic algorithm optimization. *Sci. Rep.* **2024**, *14*, 4865. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
26. Li, Z.; Tu, Z.; Yi, Z.; Xu, Y. Coordinated Control of Proton Exchange Membrane Electrolyzers and Alkaline Electrolyzers for a Wind-to-Hydrogen Islanded Microgrid. *Energies* **2024**, *17*, 2317. [[CrossRef](#)]
27. Zhang, L.; Jiang, J.; Shi, Z.; Li, H.; Ren, Q.; Yan, G.; Li, J. Phased optimal configuration of electrical, thermal, and hydrogen energy storage capacity considering demand response and load matching. *Energy Rep.* **2026**, *15*, 108935. [[CrossRef](#)]
28. Kumar, K.; Alam, M.; Dutta, V. Energy management strategy for integration of fuel cell-electrolyzer technologies in microgrid. *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* **2021**, *46*, 33738–33755. [[CrossRef](#)]
29. Chahi, S.; Aqachtoul, A.; Elamrani, A.; Ouladsine, R.; Yousfi Steiner, N.; Rochd, A.; Bakhouya, M. Techno-economic analysis of energy micro-grids with hydrogen storage and fuel cell in Moroccan farming systems. *Sci. Afr.* **2025**, *30*, e03087. [[CrossRef](#)]
30. Yoon, W.; Kim, S.; Kim, J.; Kim, H.S.; Park, J. A numerical study on energy management strategies for hydrogen consumption and SOC optimization in PEMFC vehicles. *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* **2025**, *169*, 151109. [[CrossRef](#)]
31. Tang, Y.; Min, F.; Zheng, Z.; Deng, C.; Xie, J.; Yang, H. A Two-Stage Energy Management Framework for Minimizing Degradation and Equivalent Hydrogen Consumption of Electric-Hydrogen Hybrid Energy Storage Systems in Islanded Microgrids. *IEEE Internet Things J.* **2025**, *12*, 20607–20625. [[CrossRef](#)]
32. Pramila, V.; Kannadasan, R.; Bharathsingh, J.; Rameshkumar, T.; Alsharif, M.H.; Kim, M.-K. Smart grid management: Integrating hybrid intelligent algorithms for microgrid energy optimization. *Energy Rep.* **2024**, *12*, 2997–3019. [[CrossRef](#)]
33. Cavus, M.; Allahham, A.; Adhikari, K.; Giaouris, D. A hybrid method based on logic predictive controller for flexible hybrid microgrid with plug-and-play capabilities. *Appl. Energy* **2024**, *359*, 122752. [[CrossRef](#)]
34. Zhao, H.; Zhu, Y.; Lu, K.; Li, Q.; Li, Z.; Dong, S. Edge computing and hybrid control technology for microgrids based on activity on edge networks. *Energy Convers. Econ.* **2023**, *4*, 387–400. [[CrossRef](#)]
35. Asim, A.M.; Awad, A.S.A.; Attia, M.A. Integrated optimization of energy storage and green hydrogen systems for resilient and sustainable future power grids. *Sci. Rep.* **2025**, *15*, 25656. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
36. Krichen, M. A Survey on Formal Verification and Validation Techniques for Internet of Things. *Appl. Sci.* **2023**, *13*, 8122. [[CrossRef](#)]
37. Petrakopoulou, F.; García-Tenorio, E. Evaluating hydrogen-based electricity generation using the concept of total efficiency. *Energy Convers. Manag.* **2023**, *293*, 117438. [[CrossRef](#)]
38. Zghaibeh, M.; Ben Belgacem, I.; Barhoumi, E.M.; Baloch, M.H.; Chauhdary, S.T.; Kumar, L.; Arıcı, M. Optimization of green hydrogen production in hydroelectric-photovoltaic grid connected power station. *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* **2024**, *52*, 440–453. [[CrossRef](#)]

39. i-STENTORE Project Official Website. Available online: <https://istentore.eu/> (accessed on 20 April 2026).
40. Kafetzis, A.; Ziogou, C.; Panopoulos, K.D.; Papadopoulou, S.; Seferlis, P.; Voutetakis, S. Energy management strategies based on hybrid automata for islanded microgrids with renewable sources, batteries and hydrogen. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* **2020**, *134*, 110118. [[CrossRef](#)]

Disclaimer/Publisher's Note: The statements, opinions and data contained in all publications are solely those of the individual author(s) and contributor(s) and not of MDPI and/or the editor(s). MDPI and/or the editor(s) disclaim responsibility for any injury to people or property resulting from any ideas, methods, instructions or products referred to in the content.